

Investigation of weather conditions leading to different types of lightning strikes measured in wind turbine blades

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1. ABSTRACT

The growing demand for sustainable energy has triggered the constant development of taller wind turbines with longer blades. The exposure of larger wind turbines to lightning is unquestionable, no matter if it is onshore or offshore installations. Since lightning damages are still one of the largest drivers of downtime and repair cost, understanding lightning exposure, and the protection strategies for mitigating damages, is key for lowering the Levelized Cost of Energy.

Lightning exposure is partly related to the overall lightning activity of an area, but also to the orography and weather conditions, specifically the absolute distance of the wind turbines to the thunderclouds and the direction of approach of thunderstorms. Under certain conditions tall structures can trigger the inception of upward lightning from the structures.

This paper presents an analysis of four wind power sites and the weather conditions during storms that affected the wind turbines with direct lightning strikes to the blades. The lightning measurements have been performed directly in the wind turbine blades by an appropriate lightning measuring system (Certified to Annex L of IEC 61400-24 for Local active lightning detection systems).

This work unveils how different types of meteorological conditions and terrain topography lead to different types of lightning. A better understanding of how exposure relates to the local weather in the installation area is a key factor to improve the input for the blade design processes, to perform root cause analysis of damages due to lightning and to schedule operations onsite improving cost and performance.

2. ACRONYMS AND SYMBOLS

- ECMWF: European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts [1]
- ERA5: Weather reanalysis data by ECMWF
- LKDS: Lightning Key Data System
- TTP: Time to peak
- T10to10: Time 10% front-time to 10% fall-time.

3. INTRODUCTION

The exposure of larger wind turbines to lightning is unquestionable, no matter if it is onshore or offshore installations, and lightning damages are still one of the largest drivers of downtime and repair cost [2]. Understanding lightning exposure of wind turbines is key for lowering the Levelized Cost of Energy, both when the turbines are in operation, but also during the planning phase of wind power plants.

The lightning environment can be modified by the presence of tall structures, like wind turbines. Specific types of lightning

events, such as upward lightning will not take place unless the tall structures are present, and the number and frequency of them are also related to the weather conditions in the area. Previous investigations [3] have proven that the low charge content of some low altitude cold season clouds alone is not sufficient to generate the more common downward lightning. The presence of tall structures can nonetheless enable the right conditions for incepting upward lightning from the structures that connect with the charge pockets in the clouds.

Low altitude clouds do not always mean a larger ratio of upward lightning. The most relevant factor is the absolute distance between the cloud and the tall structures. Therefore, a relatively high cloud (the distance from the cloud to ground is much larger than the tall structure height) will lead to a different distribution of lightning (in terms of downward and upward) depending on whether it is located over a flat offshore site or over an onshore site located on high altitude terrain.

In the case in which the absolute distance between the cloud and the structures is low, the dominant wind direction that determines the direction of approach of the thunderstorms to the site will lead to an uneven lightning exposure of the different wind turbines within the wind farm. Those facing the direction of approach of the thunderclouds are the ones experiencing the electric field enhancement first, and hence the turbines which are most likely to incept upward leaders towards the charge accumulation in the incoming cloud.

In this paper, specific weather variables related to thunderclouds are investigated to explore the correlation with the type of lightning measured in specific sites during thunderstorm conditions. The cloud base height and the wind direction at 700 hPa are used for this purpose.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 4 describes datasets and the methodology used for performing this study. Section 5 presents the results obtained for each of the sites under investigation in terms of weather conditions associated to thunderstorms, classification of the lightning detections performed in the wind turbines and how do the results correlate together. Section 6 presents the discussion about the results obtained and presented in the paper. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the conclusions and next steps in this research.

4. DATASETS AND METHODOLOGY

4.1 Datasets

This section describes in the first place the datasets used for the research presented in the paper.

4.1.1 Lightning dataset

The lightning data is obtained using the measurements obtained from the Lightning Key Data System (LKDS) units installed in four different wind power sites.

The LKDS [4] is a high accuracy lightning impulse measurement system designed and manufactured by Polytech

A/S. Each LKDS utilizes three lightning current measuring sensors placed one in each of the blades of the wind turbines. The measurements are performed with the following properties:

- 10MS/s sampling rate, 0.1 μ s resolution.
- 1.5s recording time, 100ms pre-trigger.
- Simultaneous recording on all three blades.
- GPS synchronized time stamp.
- Remote access of full waveform and key data.
- Key data recorded per strike and per stroke:
 - o Peak current, I_{peak} [kA]
 - o Specific energy, AI [kJ/ Ω]
 - o Charge, Q [C]
 - o dI/dt [kA/ μ s]

The key data and waveform characteristics measured by the LKDS in the different locations are used to classify the lightning strikes with respect to polarity, direction of initiation, ICC pulses, etc. This is the classification used in this paper to correlate the lightning events with the weather variables.

4.1.2 Weather variables dataset

The weather data is obtained from the ERA5 dataset, provided by ECMWF [5]. The dataset provides weather variables obtained as a result of reanalysis of weather model data, and is available from the 1950s until present date.

The weather variables selected for this study are:

- Cloud Base Height, CBH [km].
- Wind direction at 700 hPa [$^{\circ}$].
 - o The wind direction in degrees is sorted into one of the following eight compass directions: N, NE, NW, E, W, S, SE, SW.

The resolution of the weather dataset is 0.25 $^{\circ}$ latitude and longitude (approx. 30km)

4.1.3 Terrain dataset

For the onshore sites, an accurate representation of the terrain is needed to understand the absolute distance between the location of the wind turbines and the thunderclouds.

For this purpose, the high-resolution ASTER dataset available from [6] is used. The data is used with a resolution of 30m per pixel.

4.1.4 Climate zones

The location of the wind power plants is presented referring only to the climate zone in which they are located. The criteria used to define the climate zone that applies to each of the wind sites follows the Köppen-Geiger climate classification [7] [8] [9].

4.2 Methodology

This section describes the methodology followed to process the datasets to obtain the results and correlation focus of this research.

4.2.1 Site descriptions

Four sites are under investigation. Two of them are onshore sites and the other two are offshore sites.

The sites are named under a generic name and the location is anonymised by presenting the results associated to each site referred to a generic coordinate system.

The following classification is performed for the sites, using climate zones as defined by the Köppen-Geiger criteria:

Table 1. Site classification

	Type	Climate zone
Site 1	Offshore	Cfc
Site 2	Offshore	Cfc
Site 3	Onshore	Csa
Site 4	Onshore	Aw

4.2.2 Processing of lightning data

As part of the development of the LKDS, the sensors are equipped with a full set of algorithms that take care of processing the raw waveform measured in the blades and of extracting the key parameters of each strike, and each individual stroke in the strike.

Once the key parameters and the processed waveforms are available, the following criteria are used for classifying the strikes in the different categories:

- Downward lightning:
 - o Condition 1: $I_{peak} > 2kA$
 - o Condition 2: $T_{front1090} < 100\mu s$
 - o Condition 3: $\frac{T_{10to10}}{T_{front1090}} > 5$

Fig. 1. Sample waveform with the definition of parameters used for the classification of downward lightning.

- Upward lightning:
 - o Condition 1: $T_{TTP} > 100\mu s$
 - o Condition 2: $C_{Flash} > 0.3 C$

Fig. 2. Sample waveform with the definition of parameters used for the classification of upward lightning.

- Other lightning:
 - o These are low peak current events not meeting the criteria specified for the upward and downward types.
 - o Condition 1: $\frac{T_{10to10}}{T_{front1090}} < 5$

- Condition 2: $C_{Flash} < 0.3 C$

The following parameters are used to identify the waveforms:

- I_{peak} : Maximum absolute current magnitude of the lightning stroke
- $T_{front_{1090}}$: The time between 10% and 90% of I_{peak} multiplied by 1.25 as defined in [10]. If there are multiple 10% or 90% crossing in the waveform before the peak, the last 10% and the first 90% crossing before the peak is considered.
- T_{10to10} : The time between 10% of I_{peak} during the front-time until 10% of I_{peak} during the current decay. If there are multiple 10% crossings in the waveform, the last 10% is considered during the front-time whereas the first 10% crossing is considered during the fall-time.
- T_{TTP} : The time between the start of the recording of the waveform and the peak.
- C_{Flash} : Accumulated charge of the entire stroke.

In order to classify as a lightning category, all conditions for either downward, upward or unknown category need to be satisfied.

In case both conditions for upward and downward lightning are true, the algorithm checks if there is a substantial charge ($>5 C$) between the beginning of the stroke and the 10% crossing. If yes, the stroke is flagged upward lightning, and if not downward lightning.

The classification is performed on each stroke of the strike. The first stroke determines the type of lightning. The criteria for downward lightning are derived from the measured properties of return-stroke events. The highest front duration was measured to be about 80us for a positive return stroke [11]. The number was increased to 100us for the criteria to account for the low number (21) of lightning samples recorded. The minimum peak current for a return stroke was estimated to be in the range of 3.0kA to 1.5kA with 2kA being the most probable [12].

The method to identify downward, upward, and other lightning was developed by Polytech. Comparison between manual classification vs the classification based on threshold criteria resulted in an average classification accuracy of 94%.

4.2.3 Processing of weather and terrain data

The weather data from the ERA5 dataset is obtained in GRIB format. Due to the coarse resolution of the dataset, a wide area (up to 4 degrees in longitude) around each of the sites is selected and downloaded, to enable capturing the features of the weather variables under analysis.

The data is obtained for the entire period of operation of the lightning sensors in each of the sites. However, since the target of this investigation is to evaluate the weather conditions during thunderstorms that lead to lightning strikes to the wind turbines, the timestamp of the lightning strikes recorded by the LKDS is used to filter out the valid dates and times for which the weather data is processed. This way, it is possible to be sure that the results obtained from the weather data processing correspond only to thunderstorm conditions.

The files for the selected dates and times are processed and the following products are calculated:

- Wind direction distribution using geographical directions:
 - The 700 hPa wind direction is used as reference for charge carrying layers and thunderstorm movement [13].
- Average cloud base height for the entire area in the dates and times in which thunderstorms were present.

The terrain data is processed a single time to provide an accurate representation of the area on which the onshore wind turbines are installed. The cloud base height is laid over the terrain layer to investigate orographic effects affecting thundercloud position relative to the wind turbines.

For both offshore and onshore cases, the wind turbines are installed approximately in the center of the area presented.

5. RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained for each of the four sites.

5.1 Site 1

A total of 183 lightning strikes were detected for this offshore Site 1 during a period of 1.25 years.

The distribution of lightning for Site 1 is as follows:

Fig. 3. Lightning classification for Site 1.

The dominant wind direction for this site during lightning activity is N-W-SW, as presented in the following figure.

Fig. 4. Dominant wind direction during thunderstorm hours for Site 1.

The cloud base height is averaged for the thunderstorm hours during the period of analysis.

Fig. 5. Average cloud base height during thunderstorm hours for Site 1.

The representation of wind direction, cloud base height and lightning detections together (Fig. 6) shows a clear correlation between low clouds, western winds, and lightning activity at the site. Together with the lightning classification presented in Section 4.2.2, it can be concluded that the very low thunderclouds lead to an increased number of upward lightning strikes at this site and a larger exposure of the wind turbines facing the west.

Fig. 6. Distribution of wind direction, cloud base height and lightning detections for Site 1.

5.2 Site 2

Site 2 is also an offshore site located in a climate zone classified similarly as the one for Site 1. The similarities in terms of lightning activity between the two sites are evident, as it is presented in the following figure, that shows the distribution of the different types of lightning over a period of 0.8 years. The total number of detections in this period was 99.

Fig. 7. Lightning classification for Site 2.

The dominant wind direction for Site 2 is N, although Fig. 8 shows a quite scattered distribution in the direction of approach of storms to the site.

Fig. 8. Dominant wind direction during thunderstorm hours for Site 2.

The averaged cloud base height is presented in Fig. 9, and as in the previous offshore case, during thunderstorm hours the cloud base height in the wind power plant area is very low, leading to a very short distance (a few hundreds of meters) between turbine tips and thundercloud base.

Fig. 9. Average cloud base height during thunderstorm hours for Site 2.

The correlation of the weather variables to the lightning detections (Fig. 10) shows a more scattered distribution of wind directions during thunderstorms but still a very low distance between the cloud and the turbines, leading to the large percentage of upward lightning presented in Fig. 7.

Fig. 10. Distribution of wind direction, cloud base height and lightning detections for Site 2.

5.3 Site 3

Site 3 is an onshore site, located in a mountain area in a warmer climate zone. The fact that the terrain is so elevated has a clear impact on the amount and type of lightning strikes affecting the site.

The period analysed for this site is limited to only 1 month, and yet the number of strikes detected is up to 182.

Fig. 11. Lightning classification for Site 3.

The wind direction during thunderstorms in this site is clearly dominant from the SW.

Fig. 12. Dominant wind direction during thunderstorm hours for Site 3.

In this case, it is necessary to have a close look at the terrain profile before paying attention to the cloud base height distribution.

Fig. 13. 3D terrain profile for Site 3.

Looking at this terrain profile and the wind direction, the mountains play an active role on how the clouds interact with the terrain. The wind comes predominantly from the SW, meaning that the clouds will be pushed over the mountains, and the cloud bases will be extremely close to the surface or even at the same level. This reasoning is supported by the combined result of the averaged cloud base height laid over the terrain.

Fig. 14. Average cloud base height extrapolated over 3D terrain for Site 3. Wind direction represented as red arrows.

The results in Fig. 14 must be interpreted in the following way. The SW wind pushes low altitude clouds over the mountains leading to the high clouds to the East.

By the time the thunderclouds are pushed over the site, the distance to the tip of the turbines is extremely low, or even zero, meaning that the wind turbines are immersed into the clouds.

This is a very special situation, from the point of view of lightning activity to the wind turbines. Even in the case of low charge content in the clouds travelling above these mountains, the turbine blades will be so close to the charge pockets that lightning is very likely to be self-incepted from the blades.

The last result, presented in Fig. 15, for this site highlights the concentration of lightning occurrences at very low cloud base heights.

Fig. 15. Distribution of wind direction, cloud base height and lightning detections for Site 3.

5.4 Site 4

The last site investigated is also an onshore site. The climate zone corresponds to a very warm area, and with just this information higher thunderclouds leading to more downward lightning could be expected.

The lightning activity has been measured to be 247 strikes in a longer time of period of 2.25 years.

Fig. 16. Lightning classification for Site 4.

The dominant wind direction during thunderstorm hours at this site is E-SE.

Fig. 17. Dominant wind direction during thunderstorm hours for Site 4.

An overview of the terrain indicates a lower altitude than in the case of Site 3. Also, since the wind turbines are located at the center of the area investigated, it is clear from Fig. 18 that they lay over a flat terrain with mountains to the N-W-SW, and the dominant wind direction observed from Fig. 17 correlates well with this scenario.

Fig. 18. 3D terrain profile and approximate location of turbines for Site 4.

As it can be expected from a warm climate area, the thundercloud altitude is higher than in colder climates.

Fig. 19. Average cloud base height extrapolated over 3D terrain for Site 4. Wind direction represented with red arrows.

In this case, since the wind turbines are installed in the flatter area in the center of the terrain presented in Fig. 18, it is worth having a closer look at a side view of the cloud and terrain interaction, to understand what the real distance between the cloud bases and the turbines is.

Fig. 20. Average cloud base height laid over 3D terrain for Site 4 – Side View.

From Fig. 20 it is possible to conclude that there is a distance between the turbine tips and the thundercloud base of approximately 1 km. This supports the result that a larger fraction of the lightning strikes to the turbines at the site occur when the cloud base is above 1km (60% above 1km and 40% below 1km), as it is presented in the following plot.

Fig. 21. Distribution of wind direction, cloud base height and lightning detections for Site 4.

This larger gap leads to a different lightning distribution than in the other onshore site in which the turbines were immersed in the cloud, and justifies the distribution presented in Fig. 16 in which a 67.6% of the lightning strikes detected are of the downward type.

6. DISCUSSION

Section 5 has presented the results obtained for the four sites under investigation. The focus is on the type of lightning detected by the LKDS sensors in the wind turbines, and the classification is focused on the lightning direction: upwards or downwards.

According to the results obtained from this investigation there is a clear correlation between the weather parameters analysed and the type of lightning detected. Especially the impact of the cloud position relative to the wind turbines determines that a larger concentration of the upward initiated lightning is present in some of the sites.

The cloud base height is determined by different factors, mainly the climate zone and the type of terrain. In general, and according to the results obtained during this investigation, we classify low clouds as clouds with a distance to the wind turbines lower than 1km, whereas clouds are classified as high when the distance to the wind turbines is above 1km.

Cold climate zones account for lower clouds due to a lack of deep convection, especially in the colder months of the year. These lower and shallower clouds are also expected to carry a lower charge content. The reason is that the lack of vertical development also leads to a lower charge build-up. In these conditions, lightning is more difficult to develop over a flat terrain area. However, the presence of tall structures such as the wind turbines favours the development of lightning strikes of the upward type.

The turbines are tall structures bridging the gap to the already close cloud, and in this situation the intensification of electric field at the turbine blade tips due to the charge accumulation in the cloud is enough to trigger upward lightning even if the amount of charge is low.

This leads to a situation in which most lightning strikes detected at the cold offshore sites are of the upward type.

For the offshore sites with low hanging clouds, the wind direction is a very relevant parameter to consider when evaluating the exposure of the turbines to the thunderclouds.

Knowing the dominant direction of approach of the thunderstorms that will have a very short relative distance to the blade tips allows an understanding of which of them will face the storm first, and hence are most exposed to direct lightning attachment.

High altitude clouds would lead to a more even distribution of electric field over the tall structures, which implies less impact of the direction of approach of the storms, whilst the combination of low thunderclouds and defined prevalent wind direction observed at Site 1 and 2 clearly indicate that the turbines facing the wind direction will experience a higher electric field before the turbines further away (downstream), and the risk of lightning to these structures is therefore also higher. The wind direction is more consistent on Site 1 than on Site 2, which would also allow for a more accurate risk assessment of the site.

Site 3 is very special in the sense that it is onshore but at a very high altitude, as it can be seen from the terrain profile presented in Fig. 13. Being a warmer climate zone, deeper convection and, therefore, higher thunderclouds are expected. However, the presence of the elevated terrain with a flat area at sea level to the East determines a particular interaction of the thunderclouds with the terrain. In this case, the dominant wind direction enables a better understanding of the lightning conditions observed at the site. The wind is determining that the clouds move over the mountains to end up at a high-altitude position when they reach the flat area to the East. The thunderclouds themselves are not at a higher position than the mountain terrain, and therefore move over the surface, leading to a situation in which the wind turbines are extremely close and even immersed into the clouds.

Therefore, the wind turbines are very close to the charge pockets in the clouds, and the likelihood of lightning strikes to the blades increases drastically. Just as a remark, at this site, 182 strikes were detected in 1 month, compared to the 247 strikes of Site 4 in over 2 years.

Deeper convection at a warmer site will lead to higher charge content in the clouds. The position of the wind turbines with respect to the clouds and the large charge content justify the large number of upward lightning strikes detected, and it also calls for large charge transfers during the discharges, posing a higher risk for the blades in operation.

Site 4 is a more classic downward lightning situation. The turbines are installed on flat terrain and the warm climate of the area determines high altitude thunderclouds that will create an even distribution of electric field in the structures. Therefore, a larger number of downward strikes are expected and observed in this case. There are of course several upward lightning strikes that cannot be disregarded, which can be considered as “other-triggered upward lightning” because a nearby downward discharge removes the shielding charge layer otherwise keeping a state of equilibrium.

In this situation with high thunderclouds, the wind direction is less relevant since it will not significantly change the exposure of different areas of the wind power plant.

A relevant remark and future step for this investigation is the need to focus on the position of the -10°C isotherm in the thundercloud. The reason is that the -10°C layer determines the charge separation in the thundercloud and its proximity to the wind turbines will help better define the risk of lightning strikes to the blades. This parameter is very related to the occurrence of winter lightning [13] and is expected to have a significant impact in the case of low cloud-cold weather sites but also at the warm weather-high altitude site that is, as it has been presented in this paper, interacting directly with the clouds and is expected to be located very close to the -10°C layer.

7. CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

This paper has presented a study of four wind power sites located in different geographical areas and how the lightning activity detected in the wind turbines correlates to the specific weather and terrain conditions at the sites.

Relevant findings are obtained throughout this investigation, that prove that the type of lightning measured at the sites has a direct correlation with the relative distance between the turbines and the thunderclouds, but also that the orographic effects of the interaction between the terrain, the clouds and the wind also have a very relevant role in the lightning exposure of the wind turbines.

These results support the need for specific lightning exposure studies of wind power sites already during the planning phase. The interaction of the weather conditions, the structures and the terrain determine the lightning exposure of the wind turbines. The upward to downward lightning strikes ratio is not only dependent on the height of the structures. The relative distance of the thundercloud to the turbines and the direction of approach of the thunderstorms are key factors that need to be taken into account for a more accurate estimation of the lightning type distribution, beyond the traditional calculations used in the Annex B of the IEC standard for lightning protection of wind turbines [14] [15] [16].

Thanks to the outcome of this research, a step forward is taken towards a better understanding of what the lightning exposure of sites located in areas with similar conditions will be, enabling defining a better strategy for lightning protection before the blades are in operation.

As it has been mentioned already in Section 6, an important next step in this investigation is to include more relevant weather variables such as the -10°C isotherm altitude, to identify the distance of the wind turbines to the charge layer of the thunderclouds. This, together with a more detailed analysis of other weather parameters (such as instability indices and relative humidity) and a more accurate investigation of the lightning classification in different seasons will improve the understanding of the interactions between these tall structures and the thunderstorms, leading to a more complete knowledge of lightning exposure and risk to the wind turbine blades and other atmospheric electricity related phenomena, such as triboelectric charging and P-static.

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